

NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, GALWAY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The issues surrounding gender-based violence (GBV) in Ireland have been outlined in the Second National Strategy on Domestic, Sexual and Gender-Based Violence 2016-2021 and the National Strategy for Women and Girls 2017. Within the higher education sector, the statutory planning and development body for higher education, the Higher Education Authority (HEA), together with direction from the state developed and launched a National Framework in 2019, Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions Framework. It is a roadmap and toolkit of strategies and policies to be embedded in the duty of care for students and staff in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and research organisations (DES, 2019). Funding was provided to HEIs to support the creation of institutional policies and strategies to implement the National Framework. As a follow-up, on 4 August 2020, Simon Harris, Minister for Further Education and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, issued a directive to all HEIs to develop and publish, on their institutional websites, by February 2021, a specific institutional action plan, on tackling sexual violence and harassment within their institution. In order to measure the prevalence of GBV in Irish HEIs Minister Harris announced the launch of a National Staff and Student Survey on Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment in Higher Education Institutions. This survey was conducted by the HEA in April 2021. It was sent to the entire higher education staff and student population of 39,000 staff and 235,000 students in order to create a robust evidence base for further policy decisions. Each HEI will receive their individual results.

The Irish Universities Association (IUA) created policy Guidance for universities advising that institutional arrangements should be situated within a broader institutional context that focuses on prevention, support, and an institutional culture that promotes the values of respect, dignity, and integrity (IUA, 2019).

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The university has a problematic history and evidence of a previous culture of gender inequality within its academic staff. This was confirmed by the Equality Tribunal in a landmark decision in November 2014, when the Tribunal ruled that Dr Sheehy Skeffington was discriminated against based on gender, resulting in a payment of €70,000 and the offer of a senior post, if she wished to take it. Since then, NUI Galway has made significant progress in addressing gender inequality and has developed its policy instruments across all disciplines for staff and students alike. It has supported national policies and pioneered research in the area of gender-based violence (GBV) and gender equality.

The university has funded an 18-month programme to provide a best practice model on policy review, integration, and re-design. This programme will employ a policy specialist to lead a review of the policies for staff and students, to ensure integration and coherence between policies, to respond to policy gaps, and to link with examples of best practice in this area nationally and internationally.

NUI Galway addresses the national imperative to end GBV in Irish HEIs through a mix of GBV-dedicated and non-dedicated policies:

- Domestic Violence Leave Policy 2021
 - The policy is in recognition of the prevalence of domestic violence in society and the impact it may have on staff members. It aims to provide a period of paid time away from work for staff members who have suffered or are suffering from domestic violence or abuse. This leave should enable the staff member to take the time they need to seek assistance in a structured and supported environment. NUI Galway was the first university to develop a Domestic Violence Leave Policy. Minister Simon Harris has subsequently requested that all HEIs develop a similar policy.
- Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan 2021
 - Consent Framework Implementation Working Group
- Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy 2020
 - This policy is designed to address the issue of students experiencing harassment, sexual assault, or rape. It was developed prior to the staff policy and is in the process of being updated. A working group is currently reviewing the content in order to make immediate changes required, with a longer timeframe intended for a comprehensive review to take place.
- Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy 2020
- Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy 2020–2025
 - This is the first EDI strategy at NUI Galway aimed at fostering a campus culture which is welcoming, inclusive, safe, and free from discrimination;
 - Raising awareness of domestic violence on staff and students. Advocating for GBV as part of the remit of work on gender equality at the national level;
 - Developing and disseminating the Gender Pay Gap project to other HEIs nationally;
 - Implementing a Gender Equality Action Plan (GEAP) to include an intersectional approach to address the underrepresentation of minority and vulnerable groups;
 - Instituting yearly audits guided by an intersectionality frame to assess the progression of staff on the basis of gender, ethnicity, sexual orientation, disability status, and age;
 - Implement an equality impact assessment (EIA) across all policies and practices at NUI Galway.
- An Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff and Student) 2018

- A Staff Anti-Bullying Policy 2019
- A Student Anti-Bullying Policy 2018
- A Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy 2018
 - This policy outlines NUI Galway's commitment to recognising and supporting individuals' gender identity and gender expression so that all members of the university community experience a positive and accepting environment where every member is treated with dignity and respect. This policy explains the support that will be provided to people who are transgender or intersex and those who do not identify with binary gender categories.

URLs

- › NUI Galway Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan: <https://www.nuigalway.ie/media/equality/files/Consent-Framework-Implementation-Action-Plan-26022021.pdf>
- › Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy: http://www.nuigalway.ie/media/student_services/files/QA606-Student-Harassment-and-Sexual-Harassment-Policy-amended-051218.pdf
- › Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy: [http://www.nuigalway.ie/media/humanresources/publicdocuments/policiesprocedures/Harassment-and-Sexual-Harassment-Policy-\(10-9-2020\)-updated.pdf](http://www.nuigalway.ie/media/humanresources/publicdocuments/policiesprocedures/Harassment-and-Sexual-Harassment-Policy-(10-9-2020)-updated.pdf)
- › Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy 2020–2025: <https://www.nuigalway.ie/media/equality/files/Equality,-Diversity-and-Inclusion-Strategy-2020-2025.pdf>
- › Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Students): <http://www.nuigalway.ie/media/equality/files/QA152-Equal-Opportunities-Policy.pdf>
- › Staff Anti-Bullying Policy: <http://www.nuigalway.ie/media/humanresources/publicdocuments/policiesprocedures/Staff-Anti-Bullying-Policy-Final.pdf>
- › Student Anti-Bullying Policy: <https://www.nuigalway.ie/media/student-services/files/QA600-Student-Anti-Bullying-Policy.pdf>
- › Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: <http://www.nuigalway.ie/media/equality/files/QA181-Gender-Identity-and-Gender-Expression-Policy.pdf>

Entry into force:

- NUI Galway Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan: 2021
- Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy: 2018
- Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy: 2020
- Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy 2020–2025: 2020
- Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Students): 2018
- Staff Anti-Bullying Policy: 2019
- Student Anti-Bullying Policy: 2018
- Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: 2018.

TRAINING

NUI Galway's Active* Consent team conducted the original research that led to the development of the Active* Consent Programme 'Young People, Alcohol and Sex: What's Consent Got To Do

With It? Exploring How Attitudes to Alcohol Impact on Judgments about Consent to Sexual Activity' (MacNeela et al., 2014). This was followed by several further reports aimed at the higher education sector in Ireland. These include the *Smart Consent: Development, Implementation, and Evaluation of the SMART Consent Workshop on Sexual Consent for Third Level Students* (MacNeela et al, 2018) and more recently the *Active Consent USI: Sexual Experiences Survey 2020: Sexual Violence and Harassment Experiences in a National Survey of Higher Education Institutions* (Burke et al, 2020). Minister Simon Harris launched the Active Consent Toolkit, including an e-Learning module in September 2020, as a practical resource, research, and strategy development tool in line with the National Consent Framework for Irish HEIs. The online consent education programme 2020-2021, *Sexual Violence and Harassment: How to Support Yourself and Your Peers* was available for use from 15 October 2020 (DFHERIS, 2020). NUI Galway launched the Active Bystander Training in their School of Medicine in 2018 as a pilot study and subsequently rolled it out across all four colleges. Participation levels are not yet published.

Consent Framework Implementation Plan 2021

Targeted initiatives include online and in-person training programmes and workshops on active consent for students and staff. The Active* Consent Programme was developed in NUI Galway and has been run as a research programme that shares its resources with the sector nationally. At the level of the institution a consent framework coordinator post has been approved and will be coordinated through the VP for Equality, Diversity, & Inclusion. Policies are in place to manage complaints of harassment by students and by staff. This is intended to provide a transparent and consistent system for addressing staff and student complaints of sexual harassment, sexual assault, and rape. These policies are managed by the director of HR / dean of students and are under the responsibility of the employee relations manager and the dean of students. Training for students and staff on responding to the disclosure of sexual harassment and sexual assault is provided through the local rape crisis centre and programmes devised by the Active* Consent team. Seed funding was provided to develop this programme of training through the university. The university also supports the rollout of the Bystander Intervention Programme at the college level.

Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy 2020

In accordance with the H&S Code of Practice, this policy is intended to raise awareness of the issue by inclusion in staff bulletins and training at the recruitment stage and using any other appropriate method. Each unit will be provided with training on dignity at work and associated relevant policies at least once every two years.

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy 2020–2025

Consent workshops and Bystander Intervention programmes are mentioned as supports for a safe and respectful working environment. The target group are all staff and students on campus. These initiatives are provided with institutional leadership through the Vice President for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion. These workshops are ongoing.

Equal Opportunity Policy and Grievance Procedure (Staff and Student) 2018

The university seeks to provide appropriate equality and diversity training for all staff and members of committees. The training and development programmes are aimed at heads of schools/units, senior staff, line managers, and supervisors who have a particular responsibility for implementing this equality policy. All members of complaints panels complete a specific complaints panel workshop on complaints adjudication – Equality of Opportunity and Discrimination.

Staff Anti-Bullying Policy 2019

The policy foresees that it needs to be ensured that adequate training and awareness raising initiatives are in place to prevent the occurrence of bullying in the workplace and to ensure training for its proper implementation.

Student Anti-Bullying Policy 2018

Members of the NUI Galway community, including university management, heads of schools and units, all those who supervise/manage staff, and all those who interface with students, including academics, researchers, and support services staff, have the responsibility, among others, to ensure that training in relation to gender identity and expression is provided in their area.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

NUI Galway is a globally focused research-led university. Public engagement, research collaboration, and learning outputs on GBV in NUI Galway includes Dr Pdraig MacNeela's contribution in the working group on the National Consent Framework as well as his team's pioneering work on research and creating the Active* Consent Programme.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The eight policies combined address **six** forms of GBV: sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, organisational violence, online violence and other (gender-based bullying). The three policies that are GBV focused refer to sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, including their online forms. The other five policies that are not GBV focused refer to sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, organisational violence, gender-based bullying, including their online forms.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harrassment | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harrassment | |

7Ps covered: The eight policies combined cover all **7Ps** – namely, prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnerships and policies.

The number of Ps covered vary among the policies. While the NUI Galway Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan covers all Ps, the Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy covers 6Ps, and other policies cover 2 to 4Ps (see the charts below). The most commonly covered P is the provision of services (seven out of eight policies).

NUI Galway Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan:

Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy:

Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy:

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy 2020 – 2025:

Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Students):

Staff Anti-Bullying Policy:

Student Anti-Bullying Policy:

Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy:

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: All policies target academic and non-academic staff. Most of them, except for the Staff Anti-Bullying Policy, also target students. The Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy also targets third-party contractors within the control of the university in the conduct of activities relating to university operations and programmes and university-related activities on university property and off. The Staff Anti-Bullying Policy also targets members of the public experiencing bullying by university employees.

Specific vulnerable groups: The policies cover 12 vulnerable groups in total. These are (in the order of the frequency they are referred to): students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds and staff and students with disabilities, LGBTQIA+ staff and students, staff with temporary contracts, early-career researchers, staff with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, new and expectant mothers and others. Other groups include employees of other organisations, customers, and business contacts.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes. The Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Strategy 2020 – 2025 has a goal (n.2) to develop future iterations of the Gender Equality Action Plan (GEAP) to include an intersectional approach to address the underrepresentation of minority and vulnerable groups and to institute a yearly audit

guided by an intersectionality frame to assess the progression of staff on the basis of gender, ethnicity, sexual orientation, disability status, and age.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. It is addressed in the following policies:

NUI Galway Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan: Bystander Intervention Training for Staff and Students.

Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy: Bystanders are mentioned in relation to the impact GBV has not only on the victims but also on bystanders. It may also have a damaging impact on employees who are not themselves the object of unwanted behaviour but who are witness to it or have a knowledge of the unwanted behaviour. It may also have an impact on the economic efficiency of the enterprise where employees' productivity is reduced by having to work in a climate in which the individual's integrity is not respected.

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy 2020–2025: Under Goal 4, there is a task to empower staff and students to question and challenge undesirable language and behaviour without fear of repercussions and with confidence in university support for those who speak up (e.g. Active Bystander Training).

Staff Anti-Bullying Policy: Bystanders are briefly mentioned as 'colleagues'. It is university policy that every member of staff has a right to work in an environment free of any form of bullying. Aside from the impact upon the individual and colleagues, such behaviour(s) can harm working relationships, undermine morale, and damage efficiency across the workplace.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. It is addressed in the following policies:

Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy: The policy refers to perpetrators in relation to reported cases. It mentions the presumption of innocence and the confidentiality of the procedure.

Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy: That policy states that similar to the role of the complainant, the respondent (the person(s) against whom a complaint has been made) will play an important role in the successful resolution of harassment or sexual harassment complaints. Individuals involved should take the time to make themselves aware of this policy and to make use of the many other sources of information and support during the complaints process. There are a number of sources of support, advice, and assistance available for individuals such as the Line Manager Contact Person, the Employee Assistance Programme, the Designated Person, the HR Office, and others. The respondent is expected to make a reasonable and genuine attempt to fully participate in attempts to resolve the dispute. It is important to note that the presumption of innocence applies to the respondent at all stages of an investigation. The policy states that the respondent must not engage in victimisation, intimidation, or hostility towards the complainant or potential witnesses. Where a complaint has been made (either formally or informally), the respondent should not discuss the matter with potential witnesses. This is necessary to avoid compromising the complaints process.

Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Students): The respondent in a complaint will have equal rights to defend themselves in the investigation into the complaint and appeal a decision of the complaints panel. This is the same for staff, students, or members of the public.

Staff Anti-Bullying Policy: The same as in the Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy.

Student Anti-Bullying Policy: This policy addresses support for complainants and respondents, stating that “Anyone can become the victim of a bully at some point in their life. Those who bully can, at other times, also be victims themselves, redirecting their anger to someone more vulnerable than themselves. Bullying can cause severe consequences both short and long term. It is important that those involved seek appropriate support. Free and confidential help is provided by the Counselling Service.”

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. The NUI Galway Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan sets up indicators relating to prevalence and policies.

This policy will be updated for implementation by the start of the academic year 2021-22. The collection of baseline data on the prevalence of harassment, sexual harassment, and sexual violence among the student community in NUI Galway is done through the SES 2020 Survey (Student Experience Survey) and the Report and Support online system. A staff survey took place in 2021 as part of a national initiative. HR are undertaking a review of all report and baseline data in this regard. There is also the formal complaint channel that records all incidents of GBV.

Monitoring: Yes. Three out of the eight policies have a monitoring mechanism in place. All three monitor the results of the institutional procedure. Furthermore, two of them monitor the number of cases:

- *NUI Galway Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan:* number of cases, results of the institutional procedure.
- *Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy:* number of cases, results of the institutional procedure.
- *Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Student):* results of the institutional procedure.

Evaluation: Yes. It is addressed in the following policies:

NUI Galway Consent Framework Implementation Action Plan: The Consent Framework Implementation Working Group was established in September 2019 and meets every eight weeks to report on the progress of the action plan. This group reports to the Equality, Diversity, Inclusion Campus Committee, who in turn report to the University Management Team and Údarás na hOllscoile (University Governing Authority) via the Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Committee. An annual report is submitted to the HEA.

Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy and Staff Anti-Bullying Policy: These two policies will be reviewed on a biennial basis in line with experience in employment, changes in the law, relevant case law, or other developments. The director of HR is responsible for ensuring that ongoing monitoring and training take place.

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy 2020 – 2025: Goal 2 refers to proactive promotion of inclusion and equality of opportunity.

Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Students): The Governing Authority via the Equality, Diversity & Inclusion Committee (EDIC) has overall responsibility for the approval of this policy and ensuring

that the university's goal of equal opportunities for staff and students is achieved. This covers Gender and Equality in Employment/Environment GBV/Equal Opportunity.

Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy and Student Anti-Bullying Policy: These two policies will be reviewed on a biennial basis in line with student experience, changes in the law, relevant case law or other developments. The dean of students is responsible for the ongoing monitoring and review process.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Four out of the eight policies have an institutional procedure for reporting and investigation. In four cases, the procedure relates to cases between students or students and staff and in two cases to incidents among staff.

	Student vs student	Student vs staff	Staff vs staff
<i>Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy</i>	yes	yes	no
<i>Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy</i>	yes	yes	yes
<i>Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Students)</i>	yes	yes	yes
<i>Student Anti-Bullying Policy</i>	yes	yes	no

The policy defines: the institutional procedures laid out in the policies vary in detail and in the number of aspects included.

	Who to contact	How to report	Investigation procedure	Timeframe	Responsible persons	Outcomes	Sanctions
<i>Student Sexual Harassment & Harassment Policy</i>	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no
<i>Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy</i>	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
<i>Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Students)</i>	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no
<i>Staff Anti-Bullying Policy</i>	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no
<i>Student Anti-Bullying Policy</i>	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	no	no

Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy

This document is very clear on the procedure for students who are experiencing harassment, sexual harassment, or bullying. There is a complaints form attached to the end of the policy document. There is no evidence of the prevalence of complaints being recorded and very little information on supports for victims or respondents.

Complainants who feel they are being bullied are advised to use:

The informal procedure (Section 5.3 of the Policy)

How to report: The university supports the resolution of complaints, as far as is possible and appropriate, through informal processes. In many cases the problem of bullying can be resolved informally. Complainants who believe they are being bullied and wish to attempt to resolve it informally should explain the following clearly to the respondent(s):

- the details of the behaviour in question;
- the fact that it is unwelcome and offensive to them;
- the harmful effects it is having on them;
- that it is contrary to university policy;

- to facilitate this, the complainant should keep a record of events as they occur; what happened, dates, times, places, witnesses (if any), the response of the respondent(s) and the impact of this behaviour.

Who to contact: Where students find it difficult to communicate directly with the respondent(s), they should be accompanied by a third party, for example a friend, Students' Union representative, or a Contact Person. This person's role will be to provide moral support to the complainant while they are making their issues known to the respondent(s). It is not their role to make the complaint on behalf of the complainant. However, where it is evident that the complainant is having difficulty in presenting their issues, the person accompanying them will be free to assist in the presentation of the complaint. The respondent(s) should be made aware at the time the meeting is being arranged that the complainant will be accompanied at this meeting. The respondent(s) also has the right to be accompanied by a third party. Should they wish to have a person with them at the meeting, they should make the complainant aware of this at the time the meeting is being arranged.

- If at this point the parties come to an agreement or solution, the remedial actions should be clearly identified and agreed to by both parties. Both parties are encouraged to agree notes in order to remove ambiguity later. This will allow both parties to monitor the situation going forward. The objective of the informal procedure is to allow both parties agree a framework where they will be able to continue to interact together in an appropriate manner.
- If this fails to resolve the issue or if either party wishes to have the matter dealt with formally, they are entitled to refer the issue for processing through the formal procedure.

The formal procedure (Section 5.4 of the Policy)

This procedure is to be followed if:

- no resolution is reached after following the informal procedure;
- at any point during the informal procedure the complainant wishes to do so;
- the matter is too serious to be resolved in an informal way.

How to report: To begin the formal procedure, a written complaint should be addressed to the dean of students (or designated authority). The dean of students (or designated authority) will then arrange for the investigation of the complaint as set out in the Student Code of Conduct.

Content of a written complaint: in the letter of complaint, the complainant should set out as clearly and briefly as possible:

- The nature of the behaviour they are concerned about;
- The effect this behaviour has on them;
- The dates of, and the identity of any witnesses to, any incidents complained about, together with any documentary evidence of same;
- Details of any attempts that have been made to resolve the difficulties;
- If appropriate, the outcome/resolution they are seeking.

Student Anti-Bullying Policy: same as *Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy* above.

Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy

This is an institutional policy document to deal with harassment and sexual harassment of staff. All places of employment in Ireland have a policy/protocol to protect staff from this behaviour. It is a comprehensive and detailed document available to all staff. There are clear procedural guidelines to follow in the case of experiences of harassment/sexual harassment. It includes the faculty contact list and a complaints form at the end of the document as well as contact numbers for useful services.

Who to contact: If possible, the complainant should approach the respondent(s) or ask a manager to do so on their behalf, to advise of the offending behaviour and the impact which it has on the individual, and to ask that it discontinue.

Responsible persons: The complaint may refer a complaint to the next appropriate line manager. The line manager should attempt to resolve the matter locally and/or offer mediation to both parties with the intention of resolving the matter.

Investigation procedure: Pre-investigation: The complaint is referred to the employee relations manager who will appoint a designated person to oversee the complaint.

The designated person will engage with both parties to: provide relevant information, familiarise themselves with the background, contact, and details relevant to the case, encourage the use of mediation with the intention of resolving the matter.

Investigation: The employee relations manager will appoint a trained investigation team to formally investigate the complaint. The investigation team will examine the complaint and gather relevant evidence and witness statements and will complete a report for the director of HR.

Outcomes, sanctions: The director of HR will decide, based on the investigation report, if any further action is required. If either party is dissatisfied by the conduct or outcome of an investigation, they can apply for a review to assess whether policy and procedures have been followed correctly and whether the conclusions reached by the investigation team can be reasonably drawn from the evidence on the balance of probability. The review will be an external review panel.

Staff Anti-Bullying Policy: same as Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy above.

Equal Opportunities Policy (Staff & Students)

This Equal Opportunities Policy is to be read in conjunction with:

- *The NUI GALWAY Recruitment Policy*
- *The Staff Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy*
- *The Staff Anti-Bullying Policy*
- *The Student Sexual Harassment and Harassment Policy*
- *The Student Anti-Bullying Policy*

Principles:

- 2.1 A complaint of discrimination will be examined as quickly as possible with a view to resolution at as early a stage as possible. Any recommendations for further action will be clearly stated.
- 2.2 At all stages of the procedure the member of staff or student will be given the opportunity to state their case and have the right to be accompanied by a trade union/Student Union representative or a university colleague/fellow student.
- 2.3 Where an investigation raises issues of possible misconduct, reference will be made to the relevant disciplinary procedure.
- 2.4 The Equal Opportunities Grievance Procedure provides a mechanism to solve problems and no complainant shall suffer any form of victimisation as a result of raising a complaint under this procedure.
- 2.5 Nothing in this procedure may be construed as diminishing an employee or students' rights in law.
- 2.6 This procedure will be implemented in accordance with the Equal Opportunities Policy.
- 2.7 Anyone who is responsible for hearing a complaint of discrimination should have received appropriate equality training.

- 2.8 Panels convened to decide on the complaint of discrimination should reflect an appropriate gender balance.
- 2.9 Records shall be kept detailing the nature of the grievance raised, the response, any action taken, and the reasons for it. Investigation proceedings and records shall be kept confidential. Records will be retained in line with data protection legislation and related applicable university policies and procedures.
- 2.10 The principle of 'natural justice' will apply at all times in the application of this procedure. The Human Resources Guidance Note on the Principles of Natural Justice should be read in conjunction with this procedure.

Timeframe: The timelines outlined within this procedure should be treated as a guide to all parties involved in the complaints process. It is in the interests of all parties that complaints are progressed in a timely and efficient fashion. It is expected that an investigation will normally take up to 6 months to complete from receipt of the complaint in accordance with the schedule below:

- complaints should be made within six months of an incident occurring;
- complaints will be acknowledged within five working days;
- the investigation team will endeavour to conduct the investigation within 40 working days;
- the complaints panel will decide on the complaint, having received the investigation report, within 20 working days;
- the decision will be issued within ten working days of the decision being made.

During each stage of the process, the complainant and the respondent will be made aware of specific deadlines. In addition, regular updates will be given on the progress of the case. Every effort will be made to ensure that mutually agreeable dates for the investigation interviews (if required) will be set up as quickly as possible and that paperwork will be completed in a timely fashion by all parties.

For staff and students, the procedure includes informal and formal and appeals stages in the grievance process.

For the public, the complaint is addressed in writing to the head of equality of opportunities, who will deal with the complaint appropriately. The university, as a public body, is subject to review by the ombudsman. A referral of a complaint to the ombudsman is available to a complainant should they be dissatisfied with the university's response.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Nadine Shinkwin in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

